

Interview-Based Report Writing CHN-III

Awareness among Bari Imam Community Regarding Oral Health

A Cross-Sectional Study

Monica Riaz, Muhammad Nadeem, Shama Sawera, Qasr-un-Nida, Rabia Batool, Bushra Zainab,
Sumera, Shellah Akhtar, Namira Hamid, Hamza Ismai, Sohail Badsha.

Submitted to: Sir Hafiz Irfan

Community Health nursing-III

Shifa College of Nursing

Shifa Tameer-e-Millat University, Islamabad, Pakistan

February 23, 2023

Table of Content

1. Title page	1
2. Table of content	2-3
3. Abstract	4-5
4. Introduction	6-8
5. Selection of topics	8-9
6. Problem statements	9-10
7. Research objectives & questions	10
8. Significance of study	10-11
9. Aims of oral health	11-12
10. Background	12-13
11. Literature review	13-15
12. Methodology	15-16
a. Study design, sampling methodology & sampling	15-16
b. Data collection	16
13. Protection of human rights	16-17
14. Graphical analysis	17
15. Results	17-26
16. Questionnaire	26-27
17. SPSS analysis	27-29
18. Strengths & limitations of study	29-30
19. Recommendations	30-31
20. Conclusions	31-32
21. References	33-38

Comment [S11]: On the toolbar ribbon, select References. Near the left end, select Insert Table of Contents

Abstract

Introduction: Oral hygiene is a key aspect of health care for all ages, particularly for kids. There is a lack of dental hygiene among kids which is the main cause of dental issues like toothaches and bleeding gums. This study's objective is to shed light on the understanding of oral hygiene among students and to know about their attitudes & practices.

Background: Poor oral hygiene is a serious health issue in the community. We went to various schools in Bari-imam, asked students about their oral hygiene practices & discovered a paucity of knowledge on oral hygiene.

Methods: Data was collected via self-administered structured questionnaires. Students from class prep to sixth class were the intended population. Questionnaires focused on children's oral health practices & knowledge. Students under the age of 18, from both genders, were included. Pilot testing was carried out on 30 participants and after adjusting the questionnaire data was collected from 100 participants & analyzed using SPSS version 26.

Results: The findings of our pilot tests indicated that there is very little awareness of oral health (28% awareness). After the teaching session & follow-up, it was noted that their attitude & practices were improved.

Conclusions: Effective oral hygiene habits must be developed at a young age. An integrated health education and promotion approach is necessary to enhance children's knowledge, attitude, and actions towards sustaining excellent oral health followed by a comprehensive oral health care program that covers screening & management.

Keywords: Children, Dental caries, Oral care behaviors, Dental Health & Health Promotion.

Introduction

Oral hygiene is a crucial component of health care for people of all ages, but especially for children. Lack of dental hygiene in children is one of the most significant problems. The primary cause of dental problems including toothaches and bleeding gums is poor oral hygiene. Several studies' findings suggested that poor oral hygiene and lack of knowledge are primary factors in dental problems. The objective of this study is to shed light on the perceptions of oral hygiene in Islamabad's Bari-imam community. Education is important to people's lives because it enhances their knowledge and practices related to their lifestyle and enables them to distinguish between healthy and unhealthy behaviors. School being the foundational level could be the most important aspect of health education & awareness.

Developing action to strengthen the role of pediatricians in children's oral health requires an understanding of their current knowledge and practice (Dickson Swift et al.,2020)

Untreated dental caries in children causes toothache, generalized pain, and oral sepsis, leading to reduced food choices and interfering with growth, as well as affecting the cognitive development of the child in the long term (Tahani, 2022).

Two-fold impacts are evident as early dental appointments result in fewer procedures being needed and lower expenses. Childhood dental neglect can have an impact on a child's whole quality of life, including oral health, speech, nutrition, and academic performance (Perera & Nagarajan, 2022).

Notably, young children's health behavior is primarily steered by their parents, as children are unlikely to have the required capability and control over their behavior at home

Studies from Bangladesh proved dental caries were similarly linked to poor life quality, low height, weight, and body mass index (Mishu et al., 2013). The prevalence of dental decay among 6-year-olds varies significantly throughout European nations, ranging from 20% to 90% (World Health Organization, 2019). According to Chawłowska et al., (2022,), there has been witnessed a worse epidemiological situation of oral health in a few Eastern and Central European countries. Individuals' motivation to obtain oral health treatments is further diminished by a lack of understanding of the need for self-oral hygiene as the majority of children from poor socioeconomic categories in India have never seen a dentist or had a dental check-up due to financial constraints, lack of knowledge, low parental literacy rates, and restricted access to oral health care professionals (Pradhan et al., 2013).

According to the United States Department of Health and Human Services, no one can be completely healthy unless he or she is free of the burden of oral and craniofacial illnesses and ailments (Dixit et al., 2013). According to a report by World Health Organization (WHO), “dental caries is the most reported oral health disease in children. This disease has been further recognized as a pandemic whose prevalence rates in children in European countries, the UK, Japan, Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and Indonesia, have been reported by 40%, 12%, 25%, 36–85%, 38–45%, 22–61%, and 90% respectively. The given values in Iran, Senegal, and Thailand have been also in the range of 50–60%” (Abbasi-Shavazi et al., 2020).

Dental caries is regarded as a serious public health issue across the world due to its high prevalence and severe socioeconomic effect as evidenced by 60-90% of kids globally having dental caries, with the condition being particularly widespread in Asian and South American nations (Dixit et al., 2013). Several small-scale individual studies show an increasing frequency of dental caries among schoolchildren in Pakistan's main cities as researchers found a significant frequency of dental caries (56.3%). Oral hygiene is regarded as a significant predictor of oral and

dental illnesses meanwhile only 38.7% of kids in public schools and 55.3% in private schools in Karachi practiced proper dental hygiene (Khail et al., 2022). Oral health is a critical component of overall health for marginalized communities like children with specific healthcare requirements. In the interests of enhancing everyone's life experience and overall health, especially for kids with special healthcare requirements, it is crucial to offer adequate dental treatment (Alamri, 2022).

Selection of the topic

This project started when by conducting a windshield survey in the Bari imam community by our team. After that, the team visited several schools and directly assessed their status. The team traveled to numerous Bari Imam schools. Based on need & availability for access, one school was chosen. Since people lack knowledge about oral health, they were at a greater risk of developing a number several problems. Students at this school were more likely to contract infections because of their unclean teeth with the added factor that the institution lacked in epidemic team discovered that there was a critical demand for oral health education. We created a dental health questionnaire. The outcome demonstrated that they were ignorant of how to maintain oral health, including its causes, and symptoms, and recommended brushing techniques.

Pupils who had a rudimentary understanding of oral health were more likely to be vigilant and aware of potential hazards. The team tried to persuade stakeholders that education on oral health increases their sense of security and ensures that they don't become more susceptible to illnesses. It equips them with the skills necessary to control risk variables and provides assessments of the casualties. Furthermore, they will feel safer the more informed they are about

diseases, ailments, and treatments. Therefore, we selected this topic to carry out our community education project.

Problem statement

According to a report published by WHO tooth decay, thumb sucking, tongue pushing, lip sucking, and early tooth loss are a few issues that influence children's oral health. Even though permanent teeth eventually replace baby teeth, a child's entire health and well-being depend on the condition of their baby teeth. WHO stated that most children and people across the world have dental calculus, including supra- and subgingival. The main component of dental calculus is calcium phosphate mineral salts, which are deposited between and among the remains of once-viable microbes. Supragingival calculus develops throughout the dentition and can reach high levels in people that do not maintain good hygiene habits or have access to medical treatment. In these populations, gingival recession is encouraged by supragingival calculus.

According to multiple studies a quarter of five- to six-year-old children experience tooth decay, and the percentage rises above 90% in some low- and middle-income countries, indicating dental caries is a permanent public-health problem. Tooth decay in teenagers is often left addressed owing to a dearth of coverage or accessible funds. There are, however, solutions to assist families in paying for tooth decay repairs in their children. The greatest method to help children preserve their baby and permanent teeth and minimize tooth loss is to treat decay as soon as it appears (Oral Health Problems Children Face Today, 2018). After visiting the Bari imam community and observing oral hygiene's critical health problem in children of the Bari-imam community, the team's problem statement for this study is "Awareness among Bari Imam Community regarding oral health".

Research objectives

- Define the term oral health and its importance.
- Enlist the sign and symptoms of healthy and unhealthy teeth.
- Discuss the causes of teeth and gums becoming unhealthy.
- Identify the commonly applied methods of treating toothaches.
- Describe the impact of oral health on our overall health.
- Demonstrate the proper steps of brushing.
- Discuss practices of oral health in daily routine.

Research questions

- What does oral health mean and its importance?
- What are the sign and symptoms of healthy and unhealthy teeth?
- What are the causes of teeth and gums becoming unhealthy?
- What are the commonly applied methods of treating toothaches?
- What is the impact of oral health on our overall health?
- What are the proper steps for brushing?
- What are the practices of oral health in daily routine?

Significance of the study

One of the most significant global public health issues is an oral illness, which affects people of all ages. To develop an acceptable oral health care environment, understand children's oral health care needs, provide regular dental visits, and address the barriers to optimal oral health care, it is crucial to assess the level of oral diseases and the existence of oral symptoms. No profession in life can overlook the significance of dental health in daily activities, but for

school-age children, oral health is essential. Several kids were unaware of the right brushing techniques and time. They were merely brushing their teeth for a brief period outexecuted in major health problems and illness.

Delaying a visit to the dentist increases the risk of developing further issues, such as gums that bleed when they are inflamed or swollen, sensitivity, cavities, plaque, and toothaches. Youngsters frequently lack an understanding of how serious certain diseases are. This situation is even worse in countries like Pakistan with an already overburdened healthcare setup that demands the prevention of these kinds of issues. Providing education & community mobilization will ensure to spread of a sense of ownership & betterment among community members that will yield a more productive life.

The aim of Oral Health

The aim of our study is to give knowledge regarding oral health and diseases and reduce the prevalence of toothache, cavities, and tooth decay in children. Educate children about the steps of brushing at the proper time. To prevent and control oral and craniofacial diseases. Regular toothbrushing helps to remove bacteria and plaque that cause tooth decay and gum disease. Brush teeth twice a day – in the morning and before going to bed at night. Introduce toothbrushing early so that children know it as part of their daily routine. Oral Health is important to a child's overall health. Healthy teeth allow children to chew healthy foods, pay attention, learn more easily in school, and help children speak clearly.

1. **Promote** recovery.
 2. **Prevent** the situation from worsening.
 3. **Preserve** life.
- Promote a sense of safety from diseases.

- Reducing mortality rate (Through school activities based on Awareness about Oral Health).

Background

“Oral health in children is a vital aspect that can have a significant impact on their eating habits, speech development, sleeping patterns, general development, well-being, and quality of life as it is now well documented that poor dental health in children is connected with a wide range of physical, psychological, and social issues. Physical factors such as low birth weight, preterm delivery, and iron deficiency are associated with oral as well as psychological difficulties, while from a social standpoint, decreased sleep, poor learning, low self-esteem, and a high school absence rate are linked to poor pediatric oral and dental health” (Bastani et al., 2022). Therefore, education and oral health programs for the whole community are the only means to avoid dental caries.

Oral Health Promotion Programs (OHPPs) for children have been proven to be a successful intervention in the control of dental caries and are being applied worldwide in several contexts yet unfortunately, there is no economic review of their cost-effectiveness to establish the programs' value for money (Fraihat et al., 2019). Martínez-García and Hernández-Lemus (2021) stated that periodontal disease causes transient bacteremia, systemic inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction, which may all play a role in atherogenesis. Bacterial plaque on the dental surface causes gingivitis and periodontitis, which can lead to dental cavities and tooth loss.

A lack of knowledge about preventative measures, limited access to oral health services, growing sugar consumption, and limited fluoride exposure have all been related to an elevated risk of dental caries. The bulk of these oral disease risk factors are behavioral and lifestyle-

related, and they may be prevented by encouraging good dental hygiene and oral health education (Akeru et al., 2022). School-age is critical for grooming and habit formation. Cleaning one's teeth after a major meal is uncommon, especially in youngsters. During the last two decades, developing countries have experienced an increase in tooth erosion in children and adolescents. As a result, tooth decay remains a common problem, and numerous studies have indicated the need for treatments to promote oral health education and preventative behaviors.

Literature review

This is an emerging issue that looks to be critical in evaluating the importance of oral hygiene and health, as well as the role and responsibilities of caregivers in preserving the oral hygiene and health of the children in their care. The importance of oral health knowledge has been highlighted in a previous study, which aroused our interest in looking at this phenomenon among caregivers in children's care facilities. The researchers were keen to study the caregivers' knowledge and beliefs about oral health that they were utilizing to manage oral hygiene and oral health at the centers, and the findings revealed a wide range of narratives and understandings (Saleem et al., 2022).

According to the literature, the age at first dental visit varies greatly between 1 and 6 years globally as a recent questionnaire-based study found that the average age for prophylactic and diagnostic first dental visits was 4.8 and 5.4 years old, respectively (Sbricoli et al., 2022). Alshahrani et al. (2018) found that the average age of the first dental appointment was 3-6 years old. Mika et al. (2018) found that the average age of the first dental visit was 3.79 years old, with the majority of patients preferring dental treatment and just 36.9% pursuing preventative measures. American guidelines suggest that the first dental visit is at the time of the first tooth eruption.

Big top front teeth are a frequent issue that affects around one-quarter of 12-year-old youngsters in the UK. When permanent teeth erupt, the problem occurs. These teeth are particularly prone to injury, and their look can be distressing (Batista et al., 2018). Oral illnesses, including dental caries, dental tissue developmental anomalies, and periodontitis or orthodontic difficulties, have a complicated and interconnected genesis with common, mostly behavioral risk factors. (Wagner & Heinrich-Weltzien, 2017). Research has also claimed that due to oral problems over 66 million school hours per year are lost & situation is even worse in developing countries for instance, South Africa and nations like India and China had the highest rates of dental caries among four-year-old children, at 40% & 53% respectively, compared to 32% in England and 22% in Italy (Karimy et al., 2020).

Iranian children aged between 12 and 14 years are at risk of oral diseases, with the DMFT index in Iranian primary school children ranging from 3.54 to 4.2. About one-fifth of 2-4-year-old children have caries which dentists can identify, and by age 17, 80% of young people have at least one decayed tooth (Karimy et al., 2020). Oral health affects people holistically and influences each part of their personality. Problems with the mouth are a burden for healthcare as oral cancers are among the most prevalent cancers worldwide with 145,000 deaths each year (Ghantous & Elnaaj, 2017). Dental diseases such as dental caries, periodontal, tooth loss, and cancers of the lips and oral cavity are the most prevalent noncommunicable diseases globally, with significant health, social and economic impacts (Oral Health, 2023). The burden of oral diseases disproportionately affects marginalized populations and those of lower economic status.

Alrashdi et al. (2021) pointed failure to integrate oral health into pediatric practices can lead to poorer health outcomes, with significant disparities in the burden of oral diseases disproportionately affecting marginalized populations. Dental caries is a major concern in the pediatric population & despite declining prevalence and severity, the decay component remains

high. The pandemic has highlighted the need for increased focus on oral health promotion strategies and approaches to reduce the risk of oral health diseases and develop personal skills (Chhibber et al., 2022).

Methodology

Study Design, Population, Sampling & Sample Size

For this study, the research team used a cross-sectional study design; a convenience sample of 100 students was taken from a school in Bari Imam Community located in Islamabad, Pakistan. Which included population is under 18 years old students and the excluded population is above 18 years of students. For the research databases google scholar and PubMed were used. A consent form for the interview was developed and examined by the faculty at Shifa College of Nursing, Shifa Tameer-e-Millat University; a few suggestions were given according to which the consent form was modified. The consent form was developed following the guidelines mentioned in Polit and Beck, Edition 10(2021). The consent form was written first in English, and then it was translated and printed into Urdu, as it was the first language of the target population. The team informed parents about the project on oral health then parents permitted their children to sign a consent form. Questionnaires were developed, which were modified after pilot testing. It was a structured self-report instrument, consisting of closed questions; the participants were given multiple options for their answers. No Jargon was mentioned in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was first written in English and then translated into Urdu. All participants answered all the components given in the questionnaire. The interview did not take more than 15 minutes; the expected interventions were explained to the participants. No false assurances were given. The participants were all under 18 years of age.

Data collection

Before final data collection pilot testing was done by taking data from 30 participants after which the questionnaire was modified. After the selection the of final questionnaire, the team took 100 participants. A questionnaire was developed including 22 questions. It was divided into two parts; the first part was about demographic data (having 8 questions) and the second part was about the assessment of knowledge and practices of oral health in the Bari Imam Community. 14 questions covered participants' knowledge about oral health, including the importance of oral health, signs and symptoms, causes, diseases, and awareness. A total of 7 questions were about the practices of oral health.

Protection of human rights

All ethical principles were followed & confidentiality was assured. Informed consent was obtained after providing every detail about the project. No harm or any kind of monetary incentive was provided. To ensure compliance with our teaching, toothpaste was given to participants of the session which was not informed to patients priorly except to school management. Questionnaires were kept under lock & key and will be destroyed after the submission of this report.

Graphical Analysis (Graphs of research questions)

The statistical analysis was performed by using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistical analysis was utilized for computing this study's mean finding, percentages, and frequency. The data was collected via a questionnaire developed by the team. It was a convenient sample. The chi-square test was applied by using cross-tabulation. The two variables are correlated, and significant and non-significant results were identified.

SPSS Analysis

Chi-Square Tests

Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Pearson Chi-Square	7.765 ^a	2
					.021

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .13.

Chi-Square Tests

Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.990 ^a	1	.320	

Fisher's Exact Test .393 .218

a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 15.68.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Chi-Square Tests

Value df Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) Exact Sig. (2-sided) Exact Sig. (1-sided) Pearson Chi-Square 7.079^a 1 .008

Fisher's Exact Test .011 .007

a. 0 cells (.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 11.75.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Result

The result was presented by utilizing results graphs, and tables. 28% of students are aware of oral health, oral health disease, causes, signs and symptoms, risk factors, and proper steps of brushing with the proper time. In this mostly students with age 8 to 15 years who are well aware of the knowledge of oral health. These students are from classes 3 to 6. About 72% of students are not aware of oral health and related diseases. Mostly students with age 4 to 7 years who are not aware of oral health. These students are from prep class. The following are graphs showing the percentage of each class regarding knowledge of oral health.

Table 1.1: Percentage distribution for oral health meaning and its importance

Meaning of oral health and its importance	Yes	No	Percentage(%)
Prep class	1	15	16%
1 class	2	12	14%
2 class	3	11	14%
3 class	5	10	15%
4 class	4	09	13%
5 class	6	08	14%
6 class	8	06	14%
Total Participants	29	71	100%

Table 1.2 Percentage distribution for signs and symptoms of healthy and unhealthy teeth

Signs and symptoms of healthy and unhealthy teeth	Yes	No	Percentage
Prep class	1	15	16%
1 class	3	13	16%
2 class	5	12	17%
3 class	4	9	13%
4 class	6	7	13%
5 class	7	5	12%
6 class	9	4	13%
Total Participants	35	65	100%

Table 1.3 Percentage distribution for causes of teeth and gums becoming unhealthy

Causes of teeth and gums becoming unhealthy	Yes,	No	Percentage
Prep class	1	5	6%
1 class	1	6	7%
2 class	2	10	12%
3 class	4	11	15%
4 class	5	13	18%
5 class	7	11	18%
6 class	8	16	24%
Total Participants	28	72	100%

Table 1.4 Percentage distribution for commonly applied methods of treating toothaches.

Methods of treating toothaches	Yes,	No	Percentage
Prep class	0	19	19%
1 class	1	14	15%
2 class	1	12	13%
3 class	3	10	13%
4 class	4	8	12%
5 class	6	9	15%
6 class	5	8	13%
Total Participant	20	80	100%

Table 1.5 Percentage distribution for the impact of oral health on our overall health

Impact of oral on our overall health	Yes	No	Percentage
Prep class	0	19	19%
1 class	1	17	18%
2 class	2	12	14%
3 class	3	11	14%
4 class	5	9	14%
5 class	5	7	12%
6 class	6	3	9%
Total participants	22	78	100%

Table 1.6 Percentage distribution for proper steps of brushing.

Proper steps of brushing	Yes	No	Percentage
Prep class	0	14	14%

1 class	0	14	14%
2 class	1	12	13%
3 class	1	14	15%
4 class	3	12	15%
5 class	6	10	16%
6 class	7	6	13%
Total participants	18	82	100%

Table 1.7 Percentage distributions for practices of oral health in daily routine.

Practices of oral health in daily routine	Yes,	No	Percentage
Prep class	1	18	19%
1 class	2	15	17%
2 class	4	11	15%
3 class	5	10	15%
4 class	5	8	13%

5 class	6	5	11%
6 class	7	3	10%
<hr/>			
Total Participants	30	70	100%

Discussion

We did need assessment through tools such as windshield surveys, Interviews, and observation. Our group was divided into 3 subgroups with each group having males and females in it & they visited different streets & houses to collect data. The following are needs identified during the need assessment. Malnutrition, Mental health, oral health, heart disease, immunization, and infectious disease (influenza). After the need assessment, Now we have to prioritize through small group discussion (SGD).

We visited Bari Imam’s Community schools, and I found multiple health problems there but most of the school, but I observed most of the students did not brush their teeth. There is less awareness about oral hygiene among students but as we know maintaining good oral hygiene is important in improving oral health and overall well-being. We observe poor oral hygiene

including cavities and gum diseases. where we observed the needs of the community people and also observed the children in the Rotary Center's ineffective oral hygiene which may be the cause of many communicable diseases and infectious diseases. interviewed some mothers and they complain about their children's oral health e.g. tooth decay and tooth cavity. we interviewed some mothers, they tell us that their children do not maintain oral health even though they told us that children do not know the proper steps of tooth brushing. We visited Bari Imam where some ladies complain about oral health due to poor hygiene and their children from mouth diseases such as mouth ulcers and periodontal disease. The plan of action is that Discussion needs with faculty & finalization a topic using need to know & good to know criteria. Division of roles among group members regarding project planning, preparations & implementation. We select a school population of age below 18 years. We select a cross-sectional study design We make questionnaires on oral health and conduct pilot testing of 30 participants excluding the population above 18 years of students.

After data collection, we put the whole data into SPSS version 26. A result shows that the prevalence of knowledge regarding oral is 28%, and 72% of students lack knowledge regarding oral health. Due to age students of prep to class 2 are more prior to oral diseases. As our cited articles show that researchers focused on children with age 4 to 7 years old. Children eat more sugary foods as compared to adults. our articles revealed that children's health is at high risk of oral diseases and other complications such as respiratory issues and cardiovascular issues.

Primary school-aged students are an important group for interventions, as many self-regulated self-care behaviors are established at this stage in life. Our findings suggest that the group education approach merged with a planning intervention may lead to improved oral self-care behaviors such as brushing time, brushing technique, and flossing. This result is in line with previous findings stating that action and coping planning can facilitate oral hygiene behavior

when individuals have control over their behavior such as the consumption of sugary foods like candies, coke, pastries, cookies, etc.

We review 55 articles regarding oral health in children. we choose to cite 34 articles regarding oral health in children in our study. Some articles are cross-sectional studies and some articles are systematic reviews of studies. In the aspect of oral and dental health education and literacy, other results of the study have focused on the co-occurrence between social media and dietary intake and type, sugar and fluoride consumption, and the child-parent relationship. Similarly, digital technologies such as cell phone-via-mobile-application and video recording demonstrated a close co-occurrence between children's oral health behaviors. This evidence emphasized restructuring oral and dental health services and care by applying digital technology in the current century. Such a paradigm shift and restructuring of dentistry among publications demonstrate a new period of patient-oriented, technology-based, prevention-based, and outcome-centered oral and dental health service delivery for children that can shed light for researchers on new interventions. These new interventions can enable dentists and oral healthcare workers to apply modern technologies and at the same time empower the whole community particularly families, mothers, and teachers to accept digital technologies and use them for the purpose of children's oral and dental health. At the same time, according to the results of Waqas et al., despite a constant increase in applying telemedicine and teledentistry in the publications, it is notable that most of these articles are conducted in high-income developed contexts. This can open a new window of consideration for global oral health policymakers in the aspect of equality in access to technology and decreasing the digital divide.

Interestingly, and being geographically neighboring countries, lifestyles, and behaviors are not usually transposable showing, however, very similar results in most of the items evaluated in this study. To date, as far as we know, only *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2022, 19, 16004

10 of 15 one study has studied the parental perception of children's oral hygiene during the lockdown in Portugal. On the other hand, some reports from Spain have explored the influence of confinement on diet and other lifestyle behaviors, though not focusing specifically on oral health matters. Previous studies from other countries have found conflicting evidence on changes in dietary habits during the lockdown. some reported an improvement in eating patterns and others observed an increase in food intake and a higher frequency of consumption of ultra-processed foods with low nutritional value and high sugar content. The negative impact on dietary habits has been attributed to several factors, including a remote school for children.

Strengths & Limitations

This problem was the least addressed & therefore, people showed interest in learning. Sessions were well organized and coordinated. Stakeholders provided us with all the support needed. The limitation of the study was the restriction of participants' age and small size. Moreover, the team couldn't avail of technical assistance as per par. We could obtain data only once & the follow-up wasn't possible.

Recommendations

- Assess oral health risks at health maintenance and other relevant visits.
- Counsel parents and caregivers and patients on ways to reduce the frequency of exposure to sugars in foods and drinks.
- Advise parents to assist in and monitor brushing until 10 years of age.
- Build and maintain collaborative relationships with local dental providers.
- Use salt water. You can make a fresh sodium chloride solution for each rinse by dissolving half a teaspoon of salt in one glass of fresh water.
- Encourage children to brush with proper steps in their daily routine.

- Educate children about the causes of healthy and unhealthy teeth.
- Eat a balanced diet that includes cereals and grains, vegetables, fruits, dairy, and meats and beans.
- Limit the consumption of foods high in sugar and starch, and sticky foods (raisins, dried fruits, potato chips, candies).
- Avoid soft drinks, juice, energy drinks, or any type of sugary drink.
- Prepare healthy snacks that are protective against dental caries (cheese, milk).
- Teach children that they do not swallow the toothpaste.
- Educate children that Tooth brushing with fluoridated toothpaste helps make teeth stronger teeth and protects against dental decay.
- Always clean children's teeth before going to bed.
- Brush toddlers' teeth with a pea-sized drop of fluoride toothpaste for at least two minutes, twice a day.
- Place a toothbrush on the teeth at a 45-degree angle and gently brush in a circular motion.
- Clean the outside surfaces of the upper and lower teeth & brush the tongue.
- Parents and caregivers should take an active role in brushing their children's teeth.
- Use a small size brush to fit a toddler's mouth.
- Change the toothbrush every three months or when the bristles begin to wear.
- Recommend first dentist visit by age one.
- Visit a dentist at least once a year for check-ups.

Conclusion

Good oral health practices are necessary from a young age to ensure positive long-term dental health and hygiene. Positively influencing the knowledge, attitude, and behaviors of children towards sustainable good oral health requires an integrated health education and

health promotion approach. A thorough oral health care program, including screening, prevention, and management should be instituted. The latter should be established in consultation with other community healthcare providers such as dentists, physicians, and social workers. It is mandatory to educate parents and children about the importance of diet and preventive oral care to achieve optimum oral health.

Digital health technologies can widely increase access to oral health solutions make them easier to use and more accessible at all primary, secondary, and tertiary levels, and improve the effectiveness and moderate the cost of each approach. At the same time, these technologies have been applied for many purposes, from dental diagnosis and consultation to oral education and public awareness, as well as surgeries and treatments.

Sustainability

One week back after teaching we visited the school and we found that the positive attitude of children to brushing and dental flossing in the prevention of dental caries and periodontal diseases was enhanced among the peer-led health education groups suggesting a positive attitude toward preserving appropriate oral health.90% of students have brushed their teeth and remaining 10% students have some issues like 6% students have an issue that we are late so we do not brush our teeth.4% students are absent due to illness.

References

- Abbasi-Shavazi, M., Mansoorian, E., Jambarsang, S., Hosseini-Yekani, A., & Rahmanian, V. (2020a). Predictors of oral health-related quality of life in 2–5-year-old children in the South of Iran. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 18(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-020-01587-7>
- Akera, P., Kennedy, S. E., Lingam, R., Obwolo, M. J., Schutte, A. E., & Richmond, R. (2022). Effectiveness of primary school-based interventions in improving the oral health of children in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Oral Health*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-022-02291-2>
- Alamri, H. (2022). Oral Care for Children with Special Healthcare Needs in Dentistry: A Literature Review. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 11(19), 5557.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jcml1195557>
- Alrashdi, M., Limaki, M., & Alrashidi, A. A. (2021). Oral Health Knowledge Gaps and Their Impact on the Role of Pediatricians: A Multicentric Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(19), 10237.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph181910237>
- Alshahrani, N. F., Alshahrani, A. N. A., Alahmari, M. A., Almanie, A. M., Alosbi, A. M., & Togoo, R. A. (2018). First dental visit: Age, reason, and experiences of Saudi children. *European Journal of Dentistry*, 12(04), 579–584. https://doi.org/10.4103/ejd.ejd_426_17
- Bastani, P., Manchery, N., Samadbeik, M., Ha, D., & G, L., DO. (2022). Digital Health in Children’s Oral and Dental Health: An Overview and a Bibliometric Analysis. *Children (Basel)*, 9(7), 1039. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children9071039>
- Batista, K. B., Thiruvkatachari, B., Harrison, J. E., & O’Brien, K. D. (2018). Orthodontic treatment for prominent upper front teeth (Class II malocclusion) in children and

adolescents. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 2018(3).

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd003452.pub4>

- Chawłowska, E., Karasiewicz, M., Lipiak, A., Cofta, M., Fechner, B., Lewicka-Rabska, A., Pruciak, A., & Gerreth, K. (2022). Exploring the Relationships between Children's Oral Health and Parents' Oral Health Knowledge, Literacy, Behaviours and Adherence to Recommendations: A Cross-Sectional Survey. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(18), 11288. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191811288>
- Chhibber, R., Shrivastava, R., & Tandale, M. M. (2022). Addressing consequences of school closure on oral health care of children during COVID-19. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2022.725977>
- Dixit, P. B., Dixit, S., Singh, R., & Khanal, P. (2013). Oral Hygiene awareness and practices among Nepalese school children in Bhaktapur. *J. Nepal Dent. Assoc*, 13, 22-25.
- Dixit, L.P., Shakya, A., Shrestha, M., & Shrestha, A. (2013). Dental caries prevalence, oral health knowledge, and practice among indigenous Chepang school children of Nepal. *BMC Oral Health*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6831-13-20>
- Fraihat, N., Madae'en, S., Bencze, Z., Herczeg, A., & Varga, O. (2019). Clinical Effectiveness and Cost-Effectiveness of Oral-Health Promotion in Dental Caries Prevention among Children: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(15), 2668. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16152668>
- Furst, J. (2017, August 24). *The aims of first aid - the three Ps*. First Aid for Free. <https://www.firstaidforfree.com/the-aims-of-first-aid-three-ps/>
- Ghantous, Y., & Elnaaj, A., I. (2017). [GLOBAL INCIDENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF ORAL CANCER]. *Harefuah*, 156(10), 645-649.

- Karimy, M., Higgs, P., Abadi, S. S., Armoon, B., Araban, M., Rouhani, M. R., & Zamani-Alavijeh, F. (2020). Oral health behavior among school children aged 11–13 years in Saveh, Iran: an evaluation of a theory-driven intervention. *BMC Pediatrics*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-020-02381-6>
- Khail, A. A. K., Ronis, K., & Mureed, S. (2022). Dental caries and Oral hygiene status among primary school children in Quetta, Pakistan: a quantitative approach. *Journal of Pakistan Medical Association*. <https://doi.org/10.47391/jpma.5143>
- Martínez-García, M., & Hernández-Lemus, E. (2021). Periodontal Inflammation and Systemic Diseases: An Overview. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2021.709438>
- Mika, A., Mitus-Kenig, M., Zeglen, A., Drapella-Gasior, D., Rutkowska, K., & Josko-Ochojska, J. (2018). The child's first dental visit. Age, reasons, oral health status, and dental treatment needs among children in Southern Poland. *European Journal of Paediatric Dentistry : Official Journal of European Academy of Paediatric Dentistry*, 19(4), 265–270. <https://doi.org/10.23804/ejpd.2018.19.04.3>
- Mishu, M. P., Hobdell, M., Khan, M. H., Hubbard, R. M., & Sabbah, W. (2013). Relationship between Untreated Dental Caries and Weight and Height of 6- to 12-Year-Old Primary School Children in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Dentistry*, 2013, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/629675>
- [Oral Health. \(2023, February 22\). WHO | Regional Office for Africa. https://www.afro.who.int/health-topics/oral-health](https://www.afro.who.int/health-topics/oral-health)
- Oral Health Problems Children Face Today*. (2018, September 25). *Hardy Pediatric Dentistry & Orthodontics*. Retrieved February 22, 2023, from <https://www.hardypedoortho.com/oral-health-problems-children-face-today/>

- Pradhan, S., Mehta, A., Pradhan, S., & Pradhan, S. (2013). The Oral Hygiene Habits and General Oral Awareness in Public Schools in Mumbai. *Indian Journal of Laser Dentistry*, 3(2), 60–67. <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10022-1039>
- Perera, W.D. & Nagarajan, H. (2022). Knowledge, attitude, and experience of children 's first dental visit – A Survey among Chennai population. *International Journal of Community Dentistry*, 10(2), 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.56501/intjcommunitydent.v10i2.622>
- Saleem, J., Ishaq, M., Butt, M. S., Zakar, R., Malik, U., Iqbal, M., & Fischer, F. (2022). Oral health perceptions and practices of caregivers at children 's religious schools and foster care centers: a qualitative exploratory study in Lahore, Pakistan. *BMC Oral Health*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-022-02687-0>
- Sbricoli, L., Bernardi, L., Ezeddine, F., Bacci, C., & Di Fiore, A. (2022). Oral Hygiene in Adolescence: A Questionnaire-Based Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(12), 7381. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19127381>
- Wagner, Y., & Heinrich-Weltzien, R. (2017). Risk factors for dental problems: Recommendations for oral health in infancy. *Early Human Development*, 114, 16–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2017.09.009>
- World Health Organization. (2019). Ending childhood dental caries: WHO implementation manual.
- Tahani, B. (2022, December 12). *Effectiveness of an integrated model of oral health-promoting schools in improving children 's knowledge and the KAP of their parents, Iran - BMC Oral Health*. BioMed Central. <https://bmcoralhealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12903-022-02644-x>

Dickson-Swift, V., Kenny, A., Gussy, M., McCarthy, C., & Bracksley-O'Grady, S. (2020). The knowledge and practice of pediatricians in children's oral health: a scoping review. *BMC oral health*, 20(1), 211. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-020-01198-0>

Cooper AM, O'Malley LA, Elison SN, Armstrong R, Burnside G, Adair P, Dugdill L, Pine C. Primary school- based behavioral interventions for preventing caries. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013;5.

NCBI - WWW Error Blocked Diagnostic. (n.d.). <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35884023/>

Appendix
Questionnaire

Q1: Do you know about oral health care?

Q2: Do you experience gum bleeding while brushing?

Q3: Do you feel a bad smell in your mouth?

Q4: Do you use other oral hygiene tools at home?

Q5: Do you know about dental problems?

Q6: Do you know about the sign and symptoms of unhealthy teeth?

Q7: Do you have tooth decay?

Q8: Do you eat sweets (candies)?

Q9: Do you know the correct method of using the toothbrush?

Q10: Have you noticed some yellowish and white sticky spots on your teeth?

Q11: Do you notice any redness on your gums?

Q12: Do you have cavities in your teeth?

Q13: Do you use dairy products (milk, yogurt)?

Q14: Do you break solid things through your teeth?

Q15: Do you brush your teeth regularly?

Q16: How often do you brush your teeth?

Q17: How often do you use mouthwash?

Q18: How long do you brush your teeth?

Q19: Do you clean your tongue after tooth brushing?

Q20: Do you know about the cause of teeth problems?

Q21: Do you have a toothache?

Q22: How frequently do you visit a dentist?